

A Comprehensive Study of Applications of Graphene

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Abstract: Graphene, an allotrope of carbon having structure of 2D honeycomb lattice claimed as a major breakthrough in the field of material science. It is now considered as a material of the future as it can be employed both in low tech and high tech applications. Being lightweight and nearly 200 times stronger than steel, highly conductive, anti-corrosive, heat resistant and many more features, it is getting the attention of the entire scientific community. Graphene showed many remarkable features like high performance electrode for lithium ion batteries, electrode for supercapacitor, buffer layer, transport materials for solar cell applications, flexible displays, sensors, radioactive waste removal material etc. Present papers discuss about the graphene, its derivatives, properties, characterization techniques, applications in different fields. Finally, recent works in the field of graphene have been explored also. This paper can be used as a reference for future work in the field of graphene to harness its potential as Graphene poses new challenges in front of the scientific community. This consolidated review on graphene showcases the Graphene's potential in paradigm materials science and engineering.

Keywords- Graphene, Allotrope, High performance electrode, Wonder material

Introduction

Graphene is a 2D material which has an array of interlinked carbon atoms showing unbelievable strength which draws the attention of the entire scientific community. Its amazing characteristics made it a wonder material as it is sometimes around 200 times stronger than steel as per literature. Its ultra-thin nature provides it an upper hand on silicon chips which are being used in almost all electronics instruments. So it can be used to improve the performance of electronic devices by making them flexible, faster, lightweight etc. Its sheet is about one atom thick only, which is thinner than newspaper sheet. It can be stacked to form graphite, can be rolled to make buckyballs and can be rolled to form carbon nanotubes. [1]

At present, its production cost is very high around 100\$ per 100 gm as per literature. Despite of its high production cost, its potential has been employed in various fields because of its amazing and exceptional electrical, chemical, thermal, mechanical properties. It can provide flexible display in future and can turn the electronic industry into a new paradigm. [2] Graphene is the strongest, lightest, thinnest, spongelike and hardest material on the planet and its source, carbon, is virtually limitless.

Graphene- Graphene, an allotrope of carbon, is only one atom thick. It consists of a thin layer of carbon atoms which are bound in hexagonal honeycomb lattice structure.

Properties of Graphene-[7]

Impermeable specially for gases
Highly stiff

High thermal conductivity
High electrical conductivity
Transmit around 90% of the light.
Conducts very easily
Transfer electron faster than silicon
Lightweight
Hydrophobic in nature
Flexible
Transparent
200 times stronger than steel
Thinner than human hair
Highest surface area to volume ratio
Store more energy and faster charging when used in batteries
Anti-corrosive
Not available naturally
A part of graphite
Single layer of graphite
Hexagonal lattice made up of carbon
High tensile strength,
Chemical stability,
High heat transfer,
A high thermal diffusivity
High melting point

Factors affecting Graphene performance

Grain boundaries
Adlayers
Wrinkles or folds

Method of Graphene synthesis-

Top down approach- These are as follows:

Mechanical exfoliation
Pyrolysis method
Nanotube slicing
Reduction of graphite oxide
Electrochemical exfoliation
Sonication
Ball milling

Radiation based method

Graphite intercalation

Bottom up approach- These are as follows:

Deposition

Dry ice method

Growth from metal- carbon melts

Epitaxial growth on silicon carbide

Graphene Derivatives-

Graphene oxide,

Porous graphene/graphene oxide,

Reduced graphene oxide,

Graphene quantum dots.[14]

Characterization techniques

X-ray diffraction (XRD),

Attenuated total reflectance (ATR)

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR)

Ultraviolet visible (UV-vis),

Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

Raman spectroscopy

Techniques to identify defects in Graphene-

Graphene and its derivatives have defects also so its actual strength is lower than theoretically predicted.

Indirect observation through Raman Spectroscopy

Direct observation using microscopic tools like TEM,SEM, optical microscopy or AFM.[16]

Recent work in the related field

Meihui Wang et. al 2021 worked on improving of Graphene- performance by making it fold free .For this they used chemical vapour deposition method on single-crystal Cu–Ni(111) foils for developing graphene films grown as an ethylene precursor and successfully produced fold free Graphene monofilms in the temperature range 1000 k to 1030 k which has been used in field effect transistor by them.This foils can be reused after electrochemical transfer of the Graphene films.[3]

R.Naz et.al 2019 developed electrodes for supercapacitor by combining 3dimensional reduced graphene oxide 3 D RGO with Highly defective molybdenum disulfide [4]

G.Lin et.al 2019 Worked on developing anode for Lithium ion batteries(LIBs) by using graphene nanowall - Si nanocomposite (GNWs@Si) and compared the performance with lithium ion batteries with traditional graphite anode and found that . batteries with GNWs@Si anode shows better electrochemical performance.[5]

S.Bellani et.al 2019 worked on production of Graphene- through Wet-Jet Milling Exfoliation

for formation of Micro supercapacitors (MSCs) which leads to miniaturization of energy storage units and is a major breakthrough in portable electronic devices.[6]

Y.Cao et.al 2018 have reported exceptional superconductivity in Graphene superlattice which is due to the twisting of graphene sheet at 'magic angle '.They found that Twisted bilayer graphene is ideal for high Tc superconductor.[7]

Francesco Bonaccorso et.al (2016) reviewed the exfoliation strategies of graphite and other layered crystals and studied the functional ink for 2D crystal based devices which can be electronics heat resistant,anti corrosive.Graphene ink being conductive in nature, is non toxic , environment friendly and cheap also than other conducting ink.It's heat resistant property make out ideal for areas where high heat generation take place .Graphene- solar cell can be used in different ways to generate electricity by employing in mobile cases,car roofs,footpath etc.[9]

Homogeneous distribution of GO and graphene derivatives in polymeric matrix can enhance the quality and performance of composites prepared.S.K.Tiwari et.al worked on different loading of graphene oxide (GO) on the polypropylene (PP)/polycarbonate (PC) blend and found that highest reinforcement in thermomechanical propertie,Thermal stability ,high storage modulus is obtained by 1% GO loading .

MIT Researchers design 3-D forms of graphene one of the strongest, lightest materials [10]

To control electrical conductance ,optical transparency, and thermal conductance , various functional groups can be attached chemically to graphene oxide GO . Graphene oxide saturated with carboxyl groups can be utilised in energy harvesting and harmful waste utilisation.[11]

In India, Associate Professor Sathyan Subbiah and his research student Wazeem Nishad (2019) from IIT Madras have developed the simple techniques to produce graphene platelets from graphene.[12]

Moreover, India has made a new OCEAN reactor which can make a single layer of graphene in 15 minutes.

Application of graphene in real world

Graphene can be incorporated in nanocomposites for creating graphene nanocomposites which can be useful in various fields. Some of its applications are as follows:

Energy storage - A.G. Olabi et.al (2021) reported that Graphene can be used in making electrode in double layer pseudo capacitors and supercapacitor.[17] Graphene can be used as small scale energy storage like capacitors and batteries. Graphene coating can be done on graphite electrode to make hybrid electrodes.[18]. It can be useful in making energy efficient transistor, and energy storage devices.[7]

Charging of devices - It can be used for charging mobile and tablet by incorporating the Graphene based photovoltaic cell and superconductor in clothes.[7]

Thermal Management - It can be used in thermal management because of its high thermal conductivity. [7]

Flexible display - It can be useful in making flexible display OLEDs, LCDs, electronic newspapers etc.[7]

Neutralization of nuclear waste - Graphene can be used to neutralize the nuclear waste from hospital, research center, nuclear power plant, and also from houses. Graphene oxides dissolve in water very easily and can remove radioactive waste by absorbing it and forms lumps.[19]

Optoelectronics - A. Montanaro et.al (2021) worked on 67GHz Graphene field effect GFETs for optoelectronic mixing and found it suitable for mm wave applications.[20]

Bio-imaging - Graphene Quantum dots have been reported as suitable for specific cancer cell imaging and real-time molecular imaging because of its unique features like low cytotoxicity and stable photo luminescence.[21]

Frequency multiplier - J. Davey reported that Graphene shows appreciable performance in frequency multiplication that means Graphene can be utilized to develop integral multiple of input frequency.[22]

Hall effect sensors - UK-based Paragraf launched Graphene hall effect sensors GHS01AT, a plug and play hardware which can be used for analysing datasets relating to the internal structure of battery packs.[23]

Spintronics - Magnetic graphene in spintronic can be used to inject, transport and detection of the spins. It generates

electric and thermal spin currents which can be employed in spin caloritronic devices.[24]

Conductive ink - Graphene conductive ink can be prepared with binder or without binder. It can be used in sensors, automotive, electrodes and aerospace. X. Huang et.al (2016) found that printed graphene can be used for RF signal transmitting, radiating and receiving. They experimentally identify that printed Graphene can be utilized in wearable wireless technology like other technology carbon nanotubes, Silver nanowires (AgNWs) and conductive polymers.[25]

Ultraviolet lens - Electrons of graphene absorb the light photon and become a hot carrier charge conductor, when light incident on Graphene. Z. Zhing et. al sandwiched the two layers of Graphene with insulating dielectric and developed the prototype Michigan phototransistor ultra broad band. It can replace the silicon sensors used in mobile phone at present which can detect only visible light. Graphene phototransistor can lead to development of mobile phones, smart contact lenses which can work in UV and IR region of spectrum also.[26]

Radio wave absorption - B. Wu et.al (2014) reported that Graphene stacking can be used to secure enclosures by radio waves. They found that graphene-quartz substrate 90% of broadband absorption with a 28% fractional bandwidth from 125–165 GHz.[27] Graphene acts as a sponge which absorbs radioactive substance this helpful in making environment clean. [19]

Catalyst - Y. Yan reviewed the Graphene as a catalyst and reported that due to outstanding absorptivity, high compatibility with various functional groups and large surface area Graphene is suitable for using as catalyst.[28]

Sound transducers - Graphene Transducer are stronger, lighter, thinner, consume less power than dynamic speakers, which can be useful in near field sensors and near field communication. GraphAudio's Graphene Transducers are claimed as having high sensitivity, high fidelity and large bandwidth BW for data transfer.[29]

Waterproof coating - Layers of graphene create much larger surface area that prevents the dirt and water to harm the coated surface. Thus graphene can be mixed with hybrid roof coating to create protective barrier against water and dirt.[30]

Condenser coating-MIT researchers have found that Water-repellent polymer coatings used in hydroelectric power plant can be replaced by graphene coating in power plant to improve condenser efficiency and so power plant efficiency.[31]

Coolant additive-Graphene Manufacturing Group prepared concentrate of GMG graphene and glycol base heat transfer coolant (G-Coolant) which reduces the operating temperature.[32]

Piezoelectric applications-M.T.Ong et.al 2012 used designer piezoelectricity to decide where, when and how the Graphene would be deformed by applied electric field. For this they doped a single sheet of graphene on one side . Which could be used in controlling nanoscale electromechanical devices.[33]

Solar Power generation - It can be used in solar power generation in place of traditional silicon crystal as it can generate multiple electrons per incident photon while silicon crystal generates single electron per incident photon.Graphene solar cell can be used in different ways to generate electricity like Mobile cases,car roofs,footpath etc.

Leaders in the field

Graphene is a revolutionary material of the future.It can be used for developing efficient sensors, probes, and drugs.It can turn the future electronic industry.In graphene research ,as per stastica ,the graphene producing company Canadian corporation NanoXplore led the market as of may 2021.Company has expertise in Graphene based formulations for improvement of Thermoset and thermoplastic materials.[34]

Limitations of Graphene-

Its production is expensive and complex It exhibit toxic quality due to the toxic chemicals used in its production

Oxidative environment deteriorates it.[8]

Graphene's small band gap limits its practical application in transistors.[25]

Exfoliated and CVD (chemical vapor deposition) graphene sheets have very high surface resistance,

Conclusion

Graphene is flexible and the simplest and strongest material .Graphene is an invaluable material for overhauling the existing paradigm. It will lead the world with stronger, faster, and long-lasting high-performance electronics devices. Graphene discovery is a major breakthrough of the time .It is discovered because of 'need driven 'and

'discovery driven' research.There is a lot of potential in graphene which is still not harnessed well so researches should be carried out in developing high quality graphene at lower cost so that it could be commercially utilised.Much focussed attention is required in the field of large-area, high-quality graphene films and graphene derivatives to revolutionize the industry.This material and its derivatives have put new challenges in front of material scientist .It can provide tremendous research opportunities in future.Thus graphene is a need of hour.

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